

Review Article

Herbal Extracts and Plant Biomarkers: A Promising Approach in Formulation Development of Dermal and Transdermal Dosage Forms

K. Swati*

Department of Pharmaceutical Technology, Siksha "O" Anusandhan University; Bhubaneswar, Orissa; India 751030

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 14 Jul. 2025

Keywords:

Herbal Extracts, Nanoparticles, Extraction Techniques, Distillation, Soxhlation Dermal Formulations, Transdermal Dosage forms, Iontophoresis, Sonophoresis, Biomarkers Ultrasound frequency, Electrodes, Supercritical fluid Extraction, Ultrasound extraction, Cosmeceuticals and Dermaceuticals, Electroporation, Phytoconstituents, Quantum Dots, microneedle, Cosmetic technology etc

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15879012

ABSTRACT

Herbal extracts are widely used in different parts of the world as the home remedy medicines in treating various skin disease conditions like Psoriasis, Rosacea, Skin Allergies, insect Bites, bee stings and different dermal pathological conditions and cosmeceutical conditions. India is a key contributor to the development of herbal based products. To make plant-based extracts more safe, biocompatible, sustainable, ecofriendly, and devoid of adverse effects several extraction techniques were modified to extract the valuable phytoconstituents and its separation techniques which involves maceration, Infusion, digestion, percolation, decoction, Soxhlation, Fermentation, Counter current extraction, Ultra sound extraction and Supercritical Fluid Extraction. With due course of time several emerging techniques knocked the door to become a part of the treatment options for treating various skin diseases. The topical and transdermal drug delivery systems are widely used to route several macro, micro and nano sized particle through the skin with fast drug delivery to the targeted site of action and with minimal side effects avoiding the first pass metabolism. In the world of fast emerging techniques one of the first experiences of medication transfer by low frequency electricity was discovered by Hermann Munk in 1879 and termed as "Sonophoresis", "Iontophoresis" and "Electrophoresis". In future Pharmaceutical medical device applications will open a new door to deliver the drugs in a very simple, easy and time reducing manner with minimal adverse reactions on skin surfaces.

INTRODUCTION

From several decades Herbal extracts have been used to treat various skin disease conditions.

*Corresponding Author: K. Swati

Address: : Department of Pharmaceutical Technology, Siksha "O" Anusandhan University; Bhubaneswar, Orissa; India 751030

Email : swatikunipalli2@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Dermal and Transdermal drug delivery allows an improved patients safety compliance and minimizes the ecological footprint of pharmaceutical manufacturing processes. A key strategy in this evolution is the incorporation of plant-based excipients in formulation development of dermal and transdermal dosage forms. "Herbs" are obtained from plants as a raw material or their extracts. They are used in the form of active ingredient and phytoconstituents derivatives, fragrance, Flavors, colorants, anti-inflammatory, antifungal, and antibacterial agents. The Phytoconstituents derived from different extraction processes needs a strategical approach to deliver the drug particles through skin barrier in the form of micro, macro, and Nanosized particles which are termed as Nanoparticles. Novel drug delivery approach leads to the formulation development of more Bioavailable, excipient compatible, very stable, and sustainable products. Incorporating herbal nanocarriers made up of biodegradable lipids, polysaccharides, and polymers in the form of microemulsions, creams, gels, lotions, and transdermal patch transfer of drugs allows a highly absorbable, permeable, and increased onset of action on the site of action on skin. To pass the drug ions and particles in soluble or suspended form through the tissues by the passage of a direct electric current through an electrolyte solution is known as "Electrophoresis" which in turn used as a pretreatment process in transdermal patch delivery system.

Structure of the Skin and Its Role in Skin Defence Mechanism [2,4]:

Human skin is the outer covering of the body which is the largest organ in the body [Figure:1]. It is also the first line of defence. Skin contains many specialized cells and structures. It is divided into three main layers known as epidermis, dermis, and hypodermis. The subcutaneous tissue is the

outer layer of the fat and connective tissue that houses larger blood vessels and nerves. This layer is the important in the regulation of temperature of the skin itself and the body. The size of this layer varies throughout the body and from person to person. Hair follicles, sweat glands and sebaceous glands are the main skin appendages. Many medicinal plant species worldwide to treat different diseases. Skin Plays an important role to protect body from pathogens and bacteria and excessive loss of water and keep the skin hydrated. It helps to regulate body temperature, sensation, insulation, storage, and synthesis of Vitamin D by action of ultraviolet radiations. Skin keeps body water resistant and helps to absorb oxygen and helps to repair the damaged tissues and cells. Some of the common Skin Problems and treatments [Table No:1] are:

Acne; a skin condition that occurs when hair follicle become plugged with oil and dead skin cell. It causes whiteheads, blackheads, or pimples.

Eczema; It is a skin condition where patches of skin become inflamed, itchy, cracked, and rough. Some types can also cause blisters. It is an inflammation-based diseases are atopic dermatitis which is a chronic disease. The most common side effects of are skin dryness, itching, redness, scaly patches, and thickened plaques with excoriation.

Hives; Urticaria is also known as hives is a swollen, pale, red bumps or plaques on the skin that appear suddenly because of the body's reaction to certain allergens.

Rosacea; Rosacea is a common chronic skin disorder observed when face, neck, chest, or ears with flushing, persistent erythema, telangiectasias, eruption of inflamed papules, pustules, and hypertrophy with fibrosis of the sebaceous glands of the nose.

Psoriasis; Psoriasis is a common chronic immune mediated skin condition which includes redness, swelling, scaling, flaking, pruritic, skin tightness, pain and bleeding which can all have a significantly negative impact on patients physical and mental well-being.

Sunburn, Skin Eruptions and hyperpigmentation; Due to prolonged exposure of skin under sunlight leads to skin burns and suntan resulting the hyperpigmented skin which will further lead to Skin Cancer.

Insect bite and Bee Stings; a rash will appear on the surfaces of skin due to insect bite and bee stings which will lead to formation of wounds and scars and can be treated with the help of various dermal and transdermal formulations.

Mosquito Bite; a red rashes and skin eruptions appears on the surface of the skin which will lead to itching and swelling of skin which can be treated with the help of mosquito repellent creams and sprays.

Figure 1: Diagrammatic representation of Skin structure and its Function (www.google.com)

Herbal Drugs for skin Disorders [1,10]:

Table 1: List of medicinal plants with its parts, Extraction Technique, and Therapeutic Uses

Plant Name	Extraction Techniques	Phytoconstituents	Therapeutic Uses
Solanum Nigrum (Black Night Shade)	Heat reflux extraction, Soxhlet extraction, Supercritical fluid extraction	Solanin, gentisic acid, coumaric acid	Reducing Inflammation of the skin, pain, and itch
Ricinus Communis (Castor oil)	Soxhlet extraction, Solvent extraction of castor beans	Brassicasterol, campesterol, Sitosterol, Lupeol, Flavonoids, coumarins, phenolic acid, linoleic acid, Ricinoleic acid, Ricinine, Palmitic acid	Anti-inflammatory Skin rashes, Used in Hair care Products and Foot healing oils.
Jasminum Polynthum (Jasmine)	Steam distillation extraction of flowers and leaves	Benzyl acetate, linalool, Benzyl alcohol, terpineol, Nerol	Reduces the pain, itchiness of Psoriatic inflammations Used in Perfumes and deodorants
Ocimum Sanctum (Tulsi)	Soxhlet extraction method was used for leaves, Steam Distillation and Solvent Distillation	Eugenol, carvacrol, Rosmarin acid, Apigenin, Circimartinine, caryophyllene,	Treatment of acne, anti-inflammatory, Pain Relieving agent, antidote for snake bite. Used to cure

		Flavonoids like orientin and Andvicenin	Scabies and Psoriasis and itching. Antiallergic and Antileprotic.
Annona Squamosa (Custard Apple)	Maceration extraction of fruits, leaves and peel. Ultrasound assisted extraction of leaves and aerials parts of the plant	Anonain, carydine, carvone, linalool, samoquasine, Kaurenoic acid, Phenolic and Non-Phenolic alkaloids.	Antiseptic agent, Antifungal, healing wounds and cuts, used to destroy headlice
Azadirachta Indica (Neem)	Soxhlation and Solvent distillation extraction of seeds and leaves. Immersion technique.	Azadirachtin, Nimbin, Nimbidol, Gedunin, Salanin, quercetin	Antiseptic, Antipsoriatic, Chronic Leprosy, Antiseptic, Dermatitis, Skin Itching and Redness, Insect, and mosquito repellent, used as emollient and healing of sores.
Curcuma Longa (Turmeric)	Steam Distillation, Hydrodistillation and extraction using Hexane, Supercritical Fluid Extraction of dried and fresh roots.	Curcumin and essential Oils	In animal Studies daily applications of 1% w/w curcumin gel reduces the Psoriasis. Treatment of Eczema, inflamed and painful Rosacea etc.
Semecarpus anacardium (Nut tree)	Bark, Nuts and leaves of the trees are subjected to pan roasting, Drum Roasting and solvent extraction process was applied. Soxhlation with hexane is another technique	Anacardic acid, Cardol, Anacardol and Semecarpol	Treatment of Leukoderma, allergic dermatitis, Poisonous insect bites, Leprosy, wound healing, Healing of cracked feet etc.
Gloriosa Superba (Glory Lilly)	Ground seeds were percolated and macerated to extract oil. Super Critical Fluid Extraction technology.	Gloriosine, Superbine, colchicine	A paste is applied on the skin surfaces to cure Psoriasis, Skin Rashes and Dermatitis.
Metha piperata and Metha Arvensis (Peppermint)	Hydro distillation using Clevenger type apparatus. Water Steam Distillation of Leaves, Super critical fluid extraction	Menthol, Menthone, limonene, tannin, isomenthone, Pinene	Dental care and treating gums, Transdermal patches are widely used as pain relieving agents. Anti-inflammatory, Antiacne and wound healing.
Crocus Sativus (Saffron)	Flowers and stamens are subjected to ultrasound Assisted extraction	Safranal, Crocetin, Picrocrocin	Ointment is used to cure Leprosy, Oral Solution Cures Scabies, and skin ulcers
Achyranthes Aspera (Chirchira)	Dried leaves are subjected to solvent evaporation distillation method. Flowers and stem maceration and extraction.	Rutin, Genistein, chlorogenic acid, taxifolin, Saponins, triacontanol, Oleonic acid, Bisdesmosidic, Betaine	Boils and eruptions of skin, wound healing, urticaria, fungal infection, fever, and snake bite treatment. Itching and skin rashes Anticancer,
Lawsonia Inermis (Henna)	Maceration, distillation, and ultrasound assisted extraction of fresh and dried leaves. Hydro distillation of leaves.	Lawsonic acid, naphthoquinone, Tannins, Flavonoids, Quinones, Alkaloids, Saponins	The leaf paste is applied on cracked heels in rainy season due to mud infection. Antifungal like athletes' foot and sunscreen lotions.

Matricaria Chamomilla (Chamomilla)	Distillation of fresh flower buds and flower stalks	Bisabolol, Farnesene, chamazulene, apigenin, quercetin, coumarin, luteolin	Anti-inflammatory, ulcers, wounds and in Rheumatic arthritis, skin regeneration, free radical damage of skin, antiseptic properties, atopic eczema, pruritic, erythema, frostbite, insect bite, erythema, and skin rashes.
Withania Somnifera (Ashwagandha, Winter cherry)	Dried roots are subjected hydrothermal extraction process, Reflux extraction, ultrasonic extraction, supercritical fluid extraction.	Isopelletierine, anafetine, steroidal lactones, withanolides, saponins, sitoindoside	Anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, used to cure swollen hands and feet. Paste of the leaves is locally applied to kill lice infesting the scalp.
Camphora Officinarium (Camphor tree)	Solvent evaporation technique of fresh leaves and barks. Hydro distillation is also used to extract the volatile oils from the plant residues.	Camphor, linalool, 1,8-cineole, nerolidol, safrole, borneol	Transdermal patch is used as pain relieving agent, Antiallergic
Lavandula Officinalis (Lavender)	Steam distillation of Fowers, Maceration and Solvent extraction technique.	Pinnene, Linalool, Geraniol, Cineole, Linyl acetate,	Falvors and Perfume Preparation used in Skin Perfumes. Kills bacteria, and Prevents acne Brust out.
Eucalyptus alba (Eucalyptus tree)	Hydro distillation of Leaves Steam Distillation of extraction.	Eucalyptol, cineol, Polyphenols, Terpenoids	Antimicrobial, Antioxidant, Anti-inflammatory, prevents acne, pain relieving agent, Skin Lightening creams, gels, and patches

Herbal Drug Processing and Extraction Methods [7]:

The herbal extracts are highly accepted in its active form when it is extracted in the form of its phytoconstituents form. In recent years many conventional and modern methods are used to process the extraction of the herbal and medicinal plants to extract the active constituents from them. India is a rich source of Cultivation, Processing, and extraction of various useful and key phytoconstituents from plants in a very cheap and affordable technological way. A recent WHO report stated that 5.6 billion people or 80% of our world's population use herbal products for their primary health care. Herbal medicines are used to treat various skin diseases and processed in the

form of dermal and transdermal formulations. Before processing starts, the harvested herbal plants must be pre-processed. At this stage, the plants must be dried to remove moisture for preservation, preventing bacteria activity and restricting fungal growth. To increase the surface area of the dried herb plant materials for improved contact with the solvent during the subsequent extraction process, the dried plant must first be ground. An increased surface area of the dried plant materials will improve the performance of the extraction process. The particle size of the milled plants is one of the factors that can affect the extraction yield. In the extraction processes, the operating conditions can greatly affect the efficiency of a particular technique. For solid-liquid extractions, important parameters include an

appropriate solvent system, the solvent-to-herbs ratio, the particle sizes of ground and dried herbs materials, the temperature, the duration, and the agitation rate. The scale up techniques to extract various herbal constituent from plants are tabulated in the [Table no:2]

Table 2: List of Herbal drug Extraction and Processing Methods [7,9]

Herbal Extraction techniques	Processing Methods
Supercritical fluid extraction (SFE)	Supercritical fluid extraction (SFE) is one of the extraction methods in herbal processing due its ability to extract the valuable ingredients from herbs with high yield and good quality. Its favourable features include the ability to perform extractions at near-ambient temperatures, which prevents thermal degradation of the substances. SFE solvents, carbon dioxide (CO ₂) is the most established and widely used solvents. The most commonly-used solvent modifiers are methanol, ethanol, acetonitrile, acetone, water, ethyl ether and dichloromethane.
Microwave-Assisted Extraction (MAE)	Microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) is a process that uses a liquid solvent, such as water or alcohol, to extract the active ingredients from herbs. Generally, microwaves are electromagnetic radiations with a frequency from 0.3 to 300 GHz. The microwave energy is delivered directly to the herbal particle through molecular interactions with the electromagnetic field via conversions of electromagnetic energy into thermal energy. Thus, MAE typically results in a short extraction time and high extraction yield.
Sonication Extraction	In sonication processes, longitudinal waves are created as a sonic wave encounters a liquid medium, which creates regions of alternating compression and rarefaction among the molecules of the medium. In the compression cycle these vapor phases cannot remain in an expanded state, which results in rapid condensation and the release of large amounts of energy. Sonication extraction is inexpensive, an efficient tool for large-scale commercial applications, including emulsification, homogenization, extraction, crystallization, low temperature pasteurization, degassing, defoaming, both activation and inactivation of enzymes, particle-size reduction, and modification of viscosity.
Soxhlet Extraction	Selection and collection of plant materials, drying of plant materials, grinding and size reduction, size separation, sieving, Hexane, which has a narrow boiling point is the most widely solvent. The solvents used are methanol, petroleum ether, chloroform, diethyl ether, ethanol, acetone, water, and acetone.
Hydro-distillation Extraction / Hot Water Extraction	In hydro-distillation extraction, the sample and water solvent are placed in a retort. Heat is applied to heat and vaporize the mixture. Water vapor causes small sacs in the raw plant material containing essential oil to burst. Extracted oil is then transported by steam in the vapor phase into the condenser where the condensate liquid mixture formed. The liquid mixture then flows into a separator where water and the essential oil are separated by density difference. The water-rich phase, which contains some plant essence is called "hydrosol." Hot water extraction (HWE) belongs to the same category as the ASE process. The HWE however uses hot water for extraction instead of an organic solvent. The use of water as a solvent result in lower operating cost for the in HWE method because water is a cheaper solvent.
Steam-distillation Extraction	Steam-distillation includes a steam generation apparatus to supply steam to the mixture of solvent and plant raw material. Steam maybe supplied at a pressure and the corresponding saturation temperature that is sufficiently higher than the boiling point of the mixture to allow evaporation to take place at lower temperatures. Next, the evaporated mixture of water and compound flows into a condenser where it is condensed into a liquid mixture and later collected in a separator. The solvent is finally evaporated and separated from the compound using a rotary evaporator which can prevent the decomposition due to high temperatures.

Need of Novel Drug delivery Nanocarriers for “Herbal Remedies” [10,11]:

The excellent skin barrier of the stratum corneum make most of the drugs to cross the skin barriers challenging. In the realm of dermatology, the skin assumes a dual role as both an obstructive barrier and a conduit for the bequest of pharmaceutical agents. Conventional topical formulations often grapple with the intricate stratagems of transversing the multiple strata of the cutaneous mantle to attain their intended destinations. Nanotechnology[Table:3]. emerges as the intrepid answer to these challenges as it engineers nanoparticles vested with the capability to encapsulate, shield, and precisely administer therapeutic compounds to designated skin strata. The main purpose involves elevating the bioavailability and therapeutic effectiveness of these agents. As we know plant-based extracts have a varied physical and chemical properties which makes them very sensitive, hygroscopic, thermodegradable, and Fastly degrades in acidic medium. To minimize the excessive loss during the extraction, manufacturing and to make highly soluble in the blood stream and to enhance its permeability through skin at the site of action,

dermal novel drug delivery systems emerged as a more reliable and profitable form of dosage form. “Nanoparticles” are nanosized colloidal constructions made from regular engineered or modified polymers with a size range between 1 to 1000 nm. The encapsulation, entrapment, or embedment of herbal phytoconstituents into the nanoparticles is defined as herbal nanoparticles. “Dermal drug delivery “of herbal extracts are used to prevent and cure skin disorders which are tabulated in [Figure:2]. The macromolecules and nanocarrier’s are the most promising drug delivery [8,10] means:

1. To increase the efficacy and safety of phytomedicines and herbal biomarkers.
2. Study infusion and stable blood levels
3. Self-administration
4. Improved patient compliance
5. Microscale needles are more safe and painless alteration to hypodermic needle injections especially for protein biotherapeutics and vaccines.
6. The convenience of embedding the formulations into different medical devices for application on the surface of the skin

Figure 2 : Flow Chart representing challenges arises through dermal and transdermal Routes

Table:3 Types of Herbal Nano pharmaceuticals used as skincare Products [5]

Types of Nanoparticles	Composition/Advantages	Examples of Marketed formulations	Therapeutic Uses
Liposomes	Lipid Bilayers encapsulating drugs. They enhance the stability and solubility of drugs, improving their efficacy. Liposomes allow for controlled and sustained drug release, extending therapeutic effects.	Magnolol, Nux Vomica, Quercetin, Diospyrin, Myrtus Communis, Artemisia Arborescens, Puerain	Treatment of dermatitis and wound healing. Inhibiting vascular smooth muscle cells proliferation, Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant, Anticancer
Polymeric Nanoparticles	They are made up of polymers which include tailored drug release profiles, enabling precise treatment. high drug loading efficiency, reducing the need for frequent applications. Protecting the drug from degradation, ensuring stability.	Cuscuta Chinensis, Artemisinin, Berberine loaded nanoparticles	Treatment of inflammatory agents in the skin conditions like Psoriasis.
Micelles	Micelles are formed by amphiphilic molecules. Improved solubility of hydrophobic drugs, increasing bioavailability, enhanced drug stability ensuring long shelflife. Increased drug bioavailability due to their small size.	Genesxol PM, Estrasorb, Medicelle, Flucide, Basulin	They are used to deliver antiaging drugs and the reduction of oxidative stress in the skin.
Nano emulsions	Enhanced drug penetration into the skin, improving drug stability. Ability to formulate both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs and active ingredients.	Aloevera, Menthol, Lavender oil, Chamomile, Neem Oil, Tea tree oil, and green tea extract	They are used to deliver the antioxidants and the reduction of oxidative stress in the skin. It is used as antimicrobial agent and skin soothing.
Solid lipid Nanoparticles	High drug encapsulation efficiency, maximizing drug loading. Sustained drug release, prolonging therapeutic effects. Improved skin permeation, enhancing drug delivery.	Triptolide, Curcuminoids, Garlic extracts, Triglycerides	Treatment of skin eczema and dermatitis. Antifungal, Antidandruff, Antitumor.
Nanostructured lipid	Enhanced drug stability, preserving drug efficacy. Sustained drug release, maintaining therapeutic levels. Improved drug penetration into the skin.	Psoralen, Curcumin, Caffeine, Entacapone, Astaxanthin, Quercetin	Treatment of skin disorders like psoriasis. Treatment of skin Cancers etc.
Dendrimers	Highly branched macromolecules with high drug loading capacity, reducing the need for frequent applications. Potential for targeted drug delivery to specific skin layers.	Camptothecin, Berberine, Paclitaxel, Quercetin, Gallic acid, Silybin, Curcumin	Treatment of skin cancers with minimal side effects.
3D Nanogels	Enhanced drug penetration into the skin, improving drug stability. Ability to	Eupatorium Adenophora,	Treatment of dermatitis and

	formulate both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs and active ingredients. Improved drug stability and preserving drug integrity.	Cleodendron infortunatum, Sesbania Grandiflora, Withania Somniferous, Tridax Procumbens, Mannose, Aloe Barbadensis, Cassia alata Linn	wound healing. Controlled drug release for effective treatment. To Boost Fibroblast Activity and collagen production. Wound reduction and Pain Reliever activity
Magnetic Nanoparticles	Magnetic Nanoparticles are attached to the functional molecules and allow transportation to a targeted location under an external magnetic field from an electromagnet or permanent magnet.	Artemisinin, Berberine, Glycyrrhizin acid, Flavonoids, Lignin, Curcuminoids	They are used to deliver large molecules like proteins, peptides to the targeted site of action.

Transdermal drug delivery systems in herbal Medicine [9,4]:

Transdermal drug delivery systems (TDDS), also known as “patches,” are dosage forms designed to deliver a therapeutically effective amount of drug across a patient’s skin. TDD is a painless method of delivering drugs systemically by applying a drug formulation onto intact and healthy skin. The drug initially penetrates through the stratum corneum and then passes through the deeper epidermis and dermis without drug accumulation in the dermal layer. When drug reaches the dermal layer, it becomes available for systemic absorption via the dermal microcirculation. The below components are used to manufacture the TDDS Patches:

- a. **Polymer matrix:** This mainly helps to release the drug from transdermal patches depend on or controlled by the polymer. As we increase the concentration of polymer then it forms a very dense matrix which results in slow-release rate of drug. Polymer forms the backbone of transdermal drug delivery system. The drug diffusion across the polymer matrix and release rate of drug depends on the concentration and various physiochemical properties of drug as well as polymer. Examples: Gelatine, Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose, PVA (Polyvinyl Alcohol), PVC (Polyvinyl chloride), Starch, Polyvinyl Polyethylene etc.
- b. **Active ingredient:** Drug reservoir is most important component of transdermal patches. The active ingredients are selected as herbal phytoconstituents and synthetic extracts suitable for formulating according to the disease conditions.
- c. **Penetration enhancers:** These are the substances which enhance the skin permeability by enhancing properties of skin to drug. Polar pathway can be altered by causing protein conformational changes. Non-polar pathway can be altered by altering the rigidity of the lipids.
- d. **Surfactants:** These are added when drug used shows hydrophilic character. They enhance polar pathway transport of the drug. Example; Pluronic F127, SLS (sodium lauryl sulphate) Ethanol, Methanol, Glycerol, Propylene glycol.
- e. **Plasticizers:** They are used to reduce or minimize the brittleness of polymer film. They provide or give Flexibility and elasticity to the polymeric film.

- f. Drug reservoir component:** This is a component that contains one polymer or the combination of polymers in various concentrations and ratios.
- g. Backing laminates:** This helps to give and provide support. They should prevent the release of drug surface which is not in contact with skin. It should be compatible with drug and excipients. While selection the flexibility, strength, elasticity should be considered. This imparts appearance, flexibility, occlusions to transdermal drug delivery system. While selecting backing laminates the excipients compatibility should be considered. The most suitable backing laminates is the one with high flexibility. Examples; Metallic Plastic Laminates, Polyurethane, Aluminum foil.
- h. Adhesive layer:** This layer adheres the transdermal device on surface of skin at proper site and position.
- i. Release liners:** These are the protective layer which are removed before the application of transdermal patches on skin. They are helpful to prevent drug loss during storage and transportation condition. examples- Teflon, Silicon, Polyester etc.
- Percentage moisture uptake** = $[\text{Final weight} - \text{Initial weight} / \text{initial weight}] \times 100$
- c. Drug content;** A specified area of patch is to be dissolved in a suitable solvent in specific volume. Then the solution is to be filtered through a filter medium and analyse the drug contain with the suitable method (UV or HPLC technique).
- d. Uniformity of dosage unit Test;** An accurately weighed portion of the patch is to be cut into small pieces and transferred to a specific volume volumetric flask, dissolved in a suitable solvent, and sonicate for complete extraction of drug from the patch and made up to the mark with same. The resulting solution was allowed to settle for about an hour, and the supernatant was suitably diluted to give the desired concentration with suitable solvent. The solution was filtered using 0.2 μ m membrane filter and analysed by suitable analytical technique (UV or High-Performance Liquid Chromatography techniques) and the drug content per piece will be calculated.
- e. Polariscope examination;** This test is to be performed to examine the drug crystals from patch by polariscope. A specific surface area of the piece is to be kept on the object slide and observe for the drugs crystals to distinguish whether the drug is present as crystalline form or amorphous form in the patch.
- f. Peel Adhesion test;** In this test, the force required to remove an adhesive coating from a test substrate is referred to as peel adhesion. Molecular weight of adhesive polymer, the type and number of additives are the variables that determined the peel adhesion properties. A single tape is applied to a stainless-steel plate or a backing membrane of choice and then tape is pulled from the substrate at a 180°

Evaluation Parameter's for Transdermal drug delivery systems:

- a. Interaction studies;** are commonly carried out in Thermal analysis, FT-IR, Ultraviolet radiation analysis (UV), and chromatographic techniques by comparing their physicochemical characters such as assay, melting endotherms, characteristic wave numbers, absorption maxima.
- b. Percentage Moisture content;** The weighed films are to be kept in a desiccator at room temperature for 24 hrs containing saturated solution of potassium chloride. After 24 hrs the samples are reweighed.

angle, and the force required for tape removed is measured.

- g. Rolling ball tack test;** This test measures the softness of a polymer that relates to tack. In this test, stainless steel ball of 7/16 inches in diameter is released on an inclined track so that it rolls down and meets horizontal, upward facing adhesive. The distance the ball travels along the adhesive provides the measurement of tack, which is expressed in inch.
- h. Probe Tack test;** In this test, the tip of a clean probe with a defined surface roughness is brought into contact with adhesive, and when a bond is formed between probe and adhesive. The subsequent removal of the probe mechanically breaks it. The force required to pull the probe away from the adhesive at fixed rate is recorded as tack and it is expressed in grams.
- i. In vitro drug release studies;** The paddle over disc method (US Pharmacopeia apparatus V) can be employed for assessment of the release of the drug from the prepared patches.
- j. In vitro skin permeation studies.**
- k. Skin Irritation study**
- l. Stability Studies;** Stability studies are to be conducted according to the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH guidelines).

New Approaches for Herbal transdermal drug delivery systems:

Transdermal delivery has the advantage allowing sustained release of the drug. However, the drug delivery is limited owing to the barrier created by the stratum corneum. Microneedles are a transdermal drug delivery system that is painless, less invasive, and easy to self-administer, with a high drug bioavailability. The methods employed

for modifying the barrier properties of the stratum corneum to enhance the drug penetration (and absorption) through the skin can be categorized as chemical and physical methods of enhancement.

1. Chemical Enhancers; Chemical permeation enhancers can work by one or more of the following three principal mechanisms:

- Relaxation of the extremely ordered lipid structure of the stratum corneum.
- Interacting with aqueous domain of bilayer of lipid.
- Enhanced partition of the drug, by addition of co-enhancer or solvent into the stratum corneum.
- Promoting penetration and establishing drugs reservoir in the stratum corneum. Water in structure, at the lipid interface. Some of the most widely studied permeation enhancers are di-methyl sulfoxide (DMSO), di-methyl acetamide (DMA), and diethyltoluamide (DEET), propylene glycol (PG).

2. Physical Enhancers [Table:4]

- **Electroporation [Figure:3];** The use of electro-permeabilization as a method of enhancing diffusion across biological barriers. Electroporation involves the application of high voltage pulses to induce skin perturbation. High voltages (≥ 100 V) and short treatment durations (milliseconds) are most frequently employed. The technology has been successfully used to enhance the skin permeability of molecules with differing lipophilicity and size (i.e., small molecules, proteins, peptides, and oligonucleotides).
- **Iontophoresis;** This method involves enhancing the permeation of a topically applied therapeutic agent by the application of a low-level electric current, either directly to the skin or indirectly via the dosage form.

Increase in drug permeation because of this methodology can be attributed to either one or a combination of electro-repulsion (for charged solutes), electro-osmosis (for uncharged solutes), and electro-perturbation (for both charged and uncharged) mechanisms.

- **Sonophoresis;** The term sonophoresis is used to describe the effects of ultrasound on the movement of drugs through intact living skin and into the soft tissue. The mechanism of sonophoresis involves
 - **Cavitation:** Generation and oscillation of gas bubbles
 - **Thermal Effects:** Temperature Increase
 - **Mechanical Effects:** Occurrence of stress due to pressure variation induced by ultrasound.
- **Magnetophoresis;** This method involves the application of a magnetic field that acts as an external driving force to enhance the diffusion of a diamagnetic solute across the skin. Skin exposure to a magnetic field might also induce structural alterations that could contribute to an increase in permeability.
- **Thermophoresis;** The skin surface temperature is usually maintained at 32°C in humans by a range of homeostatic controls.
- **Microneedle-based devices;** The first microneedles were discovered by “Robert Chambers” in year 1921. The drug delivery device for the percutaneous administration of drugs is based on this method. These microneedles of length 50 to 110 mm will penetrate the stratum corneum and epidermis to deliver the drug from the reservoir. The Microneedles are classified into solid, hollow, coated, polymeric, and dissolvable types. The Several polymers are used to fabricate Microneedles polylactic acid, Polylactic co glycolic acid, Polycyanoacrylate etc.
- **Application of Electrical induced Techniques Transdermal Patches in**

Pharmaceutical and Cosmetic Industries [16,17]: In dermatology the principles of electrically enhanced drug delivery in transdermal drug delivery systems are now a days are used in treating various skin diseases like wound healing, treatment of burns, keloid, hypertrophic scars, psoriasis, acne, and alopecia. The cosmetic implication of skin conditions can be a source of great importance to affect the skin texture, sturdiness, regenerative properties of skin and hyperpigmentation. Several active agents are incorporated such as ionic agents, lactic acid, glycolic acid, and salicylic acid which can be used to prevent skin ageing, retinoic acid used for acne and scars, vasoactive agents are used in the treatment of cellulite such as caffeic acid, lipoic acid, and nicotinic acid. Vitamins such as ascorbic acid and its salt derivatives which can be used to treat hyperpigmentation of skin. Amino acids and peptides provided that the pH is in the range to maintain them in an ionic state. Nonionic water-soluble agents such as noisomes containing caffeine, Sorbitan monoesters, Sorbitan trioleate, Polysorbates and cholesterol used to treat cellulite and polymer-based microneedles [Table:5]. At a high frequency electrical application leads to heat emission from ultrasound which can also be damaging to the surface of the skin, and cavitation can potentially lead to tissue damage. Nanoparticle toxicity is another potential risk. Transdermal drug delivery using electrically assisted microneedle systems has emerged as a promising alternative to traditional drug administration routes. Integrating iontophoresis, electrophoresis and sonophoresis with that of the microneedle technology has shown a significant improvement in treating various skin conditions [14,15]. Optimal and low

frequency Sonophoresis will be painless and have minimal to no risk.

Figure 3: Diagrammatic Representation of various electrically assisted drug delivery through skin

Table 4: Electrically assisted synthetic microneedle through iontophoresis and Sonophoresis:

Delivered Drug	Therapeutic Application	Microneedle and Iontophoretic Characteristics	Experimental Method	Results
Pilocarpine	Palmar sweating	Microneedle; Microinjection molding machine, Japan; 193 needles; Height (875) and width (190/35) μm . Iontophoresis; 0.5 mA/cm^2 for 5 mins.	Healthy Young Adults	Increased skin permeability and sweat production on palm.
Methotrexate	Psoriasis	Microneedle; Dr Pen™ ULTIMA A6, USA Height 1mm for 10s and microporation with a needle height of 0.5 mm for 5s. Iontophoresis; 0.2 and 0.5 Ma/Cm^2 for 4 hrs	Franz Diffusion Cells (Healthy and Psoriatic human skin)	a) Higher Methotrexate delivery in psoriatic skin. b) Reduced lag time for methotrexate delivery in psoriatic skin. c) Faster Therapeutic effect d) Diseased skin shows altered drug penetration characteristics.
Ropinirole Hydrochloride	Parkinson's Disease	Microneedle; Admin Patch, 187 needles, Height (600) and tip width (48.64) μm Iontophoresis; 0.2 mA/cm^2 for 1 hr.	Franz diffusion cell (Porcine ear skin)	Controlled delivery of ropinirole hydrochloride for Parkinson's treatment.
Diclofenac Sodium	NSAID	Microneedle; Dissolving, 100 needles, Height (395) μm	Franz diffusion cell (Dermatomed human skin)	a) Increased absorption of diclofenac sodium. b) Enhanced systematic exposure of the drug.

		Iontophoresis; 0.5 mA/cm ² for 2 hr.		
Ibuprofen sodium	Pain /anti-inflammatory	Microneedle; Dissolving; Height (610 – 650) and width (307 – 306) µm Iontophoresis; 0.5 mA/cm ² for 15 mins to 6 hrs	Franz diffusion cell (Neonatal Porcine skin)	Improved delivery when combined with hydrogel forming Microneedles
Dexamethasone Sodium Phosphate	Hind paw oedema / Inflammatory disorders	Microneedles; Dissolving, 100 needles, Height (424) µm, array thickness (7.96) mm and width of (0.95) mm Iontophoresis; 0.5 mA/cm ² for 300 mins	Wister albino rats	a) Reduced oedematous fluid in rat hind paws more effectively than microneedle alone. b) Reduced levels of Pro-inflammatory cytokines.
Ce6(DOX)@Caco₃NPs	Melanoma	Microneedles; Dissolving, 100 needles, 10X10 array, height (850), base (400) and base (700) µm Iontophoresis; 1.5 Ma for 4 hrs	C57BL/6 Female melanoma mice	a) Enabled therapeutic NPs to penetrate deep skin layers and release drugs rapidly in acidic tumour tissues b) Showed Superior tumour inhibition compared to the Microneedle patch alone.
Nucleic acids	Dermatology and vaccination	Microneedles; Derma roller system 600 series Germany. 10 rows of needles on head with 60 units per row. 0.5, 1.0- and 1.5-mm long models Electroporation; 10 electrical pulse, voltage 50,70 or 100V; 10 ms, pulse duration; 1s pulse interval	C57BL/6J MICE	a) Successfully delivered gene and siRNA to mouse skin using microneedle roller assisted electroporation. b) Achieved significant gene silencing with anti SCDI siRNA. c) Promising approach for in vivo delivery of various nucleic acids to skin with potential clinical applications in dermatology.
Epidermal growth factor	Wound healing	Microneedles; Dissolving; 10 needles, 7x7 mm patch; height (550) and base with (300) and needles spacing of 500 µm. Electroporation; 20V, 1Ma, 11Nc, 10s	Kumming mice	a) Improved Epidermal growth factor Pharmacodynamics. b) Improved drug efficacy

Table: 5 Herbal Transdermal drug delivery through polymer loaded microneedles [21,22]

Disease name	Delivered Drug	Microneedles (MNs)	Related patents/ Patent No
Melanoma	Paclitaxel (150µg)	Dissolving MNs; 12 × 12 array, 800 µm height, and 300 µm base width	a) Hydrothermal response microneedle patch as well as preparation method and application (CN116687833A) b) Soluble microneedle containing antibody coupled albumin paclitaxel nanodrug as well as preparation method and application of soluble microneedle (CN116687833A)
Melanoma	curcumin	Hydrogel MNs 11 × 11 array, 600 µm height, and 300 µm base width	a) Gelatin methacryloyl-based microneedle patches for delivery of water-insoluble drug (US2023145564A1)
Wound healing	Curcumin (122 µg)	Hydrogel MNs; 15 × 15 array, 345 µm height and 250 µm base width	
Wound healing	Tannic acid	Hydrogel MNs; 20 × 20 array, 770 µm height, and 410 µm base width	
Polymicrobial biofilms-infected wounds	Carvacrol	Hollow MNs (AdminPen 1500); 1400 µm height	Surface-Charge Tuned Polymeric Nano emulsions for Carvacrol Delivery in Interkingdom Biofilms. 2019 (Patel et al)
Rheumatoid arthritis	Tetrandrine (1.5%w/w)	Dissolving MNs; 15 × 15 array, 500 µm height	Sinomenine and total glucosides of paeony loaded photothermal driving motor microneedle for treating rheumatoid arthritis and preparation method (CN117338922A)
Gout	Colchicine (48 µg)	Dissolving MNs; 20 × 20 array, 525–542 µm height and 353–370 µm base width	Colchicine hydrogel microneedle and preparation method (WO2024051132A1)
Gout	Colchicine (30–35 µg)	Dissolving MNs 12 × 12 array, 800 µm height and 300 µm base width	Colchicine soluble microneedle patch and preparation method (WO2021143951A2)
Psoriasis	Epigallocatechin-3gallate/ Dexamethasone	Dissolving MNs; 600 µm height and 300 µm base width	Microneedle patch for delivering an active ingredient to skin. (W02016155891A1)
Psoriasis	Epigallocatechin-3-gallate/Methotrexate (157 µg/5.6 µg)	Hydrogel MNs, 10 × 10 array, 650 µm height and 200 µm base width	
Hyperpigmentation	Resveratrol	Dissolving MNs; 11 × 11 array, 600 µm	

		height and 300 base width	a) Whitening and freckle-removing composition, whitening and freckle-removing soluble microneedle patch and preparation method (CN111920699A) b) Antiaging composition capable of activating cells and preparation method (CN113546153A)
Hyperpigmentation	Resveratrol/alpha-Arbutin (13.4 µg/67 µg)	Dissolving MNs; 11 × 11 array, 575 µm height and 289 µm base width	
Hyperpigmentation	Ascorbic acid/Vitamin A (90 µg/27.4 µg)	Dissolving MNs; 10 × 10 array, 600 µm height and 300 µm base width	Soluble microneedle for transdermal delivery containing ascorbic acid derivative manufacturing method thereof and transdermal delivery patch comprising the same (KR20220037994A)
Alopecia	Quercetin	Dissolving MNs 20 × 20 array, 600 µm height	Microneedle particles, compositions, and methods of treatment and delivering a substance of interest. (US11291816B2)
Hypertrophic scar	Shikonin (30.76 µg)	Dissolving MNs 10 × 10 array, 1000 µm height and 300 µm base width	Application of shikonin and its derivatives in pharmaceutical industry (CN1399957A)
Atopic dermatitis	Curcumin/Gallic acid (225 µg/117 µg)	Dissolving MNs; 9 × 9 array, 600 µm height and 300 µm base width	-
Obesity	Capsaicin	Dissolving MNs 10 × 10 array, 600 µm height and 300 µm base width	Inhibition of the activity of the capsaicin receptor in the treatment of obesity or obesity-related diseases and disorders. 2005 (US7879866B2)
Obesity	Rutin (8 mg)	Dissolving MNs 10 × 10 array, 1000 µm height and 300 µm base width	
Malaria	Artemether/Lumefantrine	Dissolving MNs; 11 × 11 array, 800 µm height	Preparation methods of intradermal microneedle preparation of artemisinin Derivative (CN104382884A)
Malaria	Artemether/Lumefantrine (1580 µg/1500 µg)	Dissolving MNs; 19 × 19 array, 600 µm height and 300 µm base width/14 × 14 array, 600 µm height and 400 µm base width	
Acne vulgaris	Azelaic acid/Matrine (201 µg/259 µg) Epigallocatechin gallate	Dissolving MNs; 12 × 12 array, 500 µm height and 300 µm base width	Soluble micro needle with antiacne effect and preparation method (CN108904299A)

Anti-inflammatory/ analgesic effects	Total alkaloids isolated from Aconitum sinomontanum	Solid MNs; 250 μm height and 100 μm base width	Microneedles and methods of manufacture,2019 (W0202025210A1)
---	--	--	--

Quantum dots incorporated Microneedle Transdermal drug delivery system [16,27]:

Quantum dots (QDs) are luminescent nanocrystals with rich surface chemistry and unique optical properties that make them useful as probes or carriers for traceable targeted delivery and therapy applications. Quantum dots can be functionalized to target specific cells or tissues by conjugating them with targeting ligands. Owing to their small size, excellent brightness, and long photostability, quantum dots have enormous medicinal potential. They have shown potential in drug delivery, bioimaging, and sensing to improve medication therapy, disease diagnostics, and monitoring. Quantum dots can be functionalized with biocompatible coatings and coupled with pharmaceuticals for targeted distribution, decreasing off-target effects and regulating drug release at the site of action. They can also improve the absorption of cellular drugs. Quantum dots great resolution and low background noise make them ideal contrast agents for bioimaging. Biodegradable microneedles are available in both solid and hollow forms. One technical challenge with biodegradable microneedles involves making devices with sufficient fracture resistance to pierce the stratum corneum without fracture. Polymeric microneedles are usually fabricated using the

micro molding technique; water evaporation, UV light curing, and heat curing are often used to create the solid microneedle device from the liquid precursor. Carboxymethyl cellulose, Gantrez AN material, fibroin dextran, chitosan, poly methyl vinyl, polylactic-co-glycolic acid, and poly glycolic-acid are commonly solidified by drying or water evaporation. Polyethylene glycol diacrylate and polylactic acid resins containing a photo initiator are cured using UV light. Polyvinylpyrrolidone is mixed with thermoinitiator that is solidified by heating at 60 °C for 5 hours. Herbal medicine carbon dots derived from herbal medicine have become the most recent incomer in the family of carbon dots. carbon dots are discovered by Scrivens in early 2004, carbon dots (CDs) are emerging as a novel nanomaterial which is smaller than 10 nm in size. carbon dots not only possess the merits from traditional semiconductors (inorganic quantum dots, etc.) and small molecules (fluorophores, etc.) but also exhibit unique properties such as photobleaching resistance, photostability, good biocompatibility and stable physicochemical characteristics. Various herbal phytoconstituents are derived from the different plant parts and they are macerated or carbonized with hydrothermal technique and fabricated into Herbal carbon quantum dots which are represented in [Figure:4]

Figure 4: Schematic representation of Quantum dots microneedle through the Iontophoresis technique through the skin

Applications of Quantum dots in Imaging techniques and Biomedical research [28,29]:

Quantum dots, the most important route of delivery at present appears to be systemic distribution through parenteral delivery, although occupational and environmental exposures via dermal and inhalation routes are also possible. Quantum dots are absorbed at cellular level through receptor mediated endocytic mechanism. The targeted Quantum dots are incorporated in the cell by the endocytic pathway via mediated uptake mechanism, and Quantum dots targeting studies have shown that Quantum dots with targeting functional groups can be accumulated in selected target tissues upon i.e. administration. Some of the applications of Quantum dots are listed below:

- More efficient and stable synthesis
- Identification of active ingredients
- Clarification of metabolism and distribution in vivo
- Exploration of different kinds of herbal medicine phytoconstituents.
- Reductions of toxicity and increasing efficiency
- Recycle of herbal residues.
- Higher extinction coefficients
- Less photobleaching
- Absorbance and emissions tunable with size

- Broad excitation windows but narrow emission peaks
- Multiple Quantum dots can be used in the same assay with minimal interference with each other
- Toxicity may be less than that of conventional organic dyes

Future challenges and scope for formulation development of electrically assisted Transdermal and dermal formulations [30]:

Formulation development will be key to the successful exploration of new technologies since the formulation:

- Ensures the stability and activity of the therapeutic agent – e.g. for Biotechnology-derived drugs.
- Determines the interface with the skin and so must be adapted to facilitate drug partitioning – e.g. into microporated skin.
- Optimizes drug delivery efficiency to maximize the fraction of drug content delivered to the body and to minimize the amount retained within the formulations. Therefore, more efforts must be focused on formulation design and development so that the potential of the new delivery technologies can be fully utilized.

d. Minimal adverse effects and good absorption through skin.

Significant efforts have been devoted to developing strategies to overcome the impermeability of intact human skin, which provides the main barrier for drug penetration. These strategies involve chemical (formulation-based) and physical penetration enhancement techniques. Chemical penetration enhancement methods involve the manipulation of the drug or vehicle to enhance the drug diffusion through the skin; this also includes the use of different nanocarriers (e.g., vesicles, nanoparticles, etc.). Among physical methods, Iontophoresis, Electroporation, and ultrasound are the most studied enhancement methods. The primary focus of this special issue is to address the opportunities and challenges associated with transdermal drug delivery and to demonstrate how various percutaneous penetration enhancement strategies can overcome these challenges, thereby improving the therapeutic efficacy of Transdermal drug delivery system. Sonophoretic research includes the application of various drugs, dual-frequency sonophoresis, combined transdermal drug delivery techniques, and the use of nanoparticles to carry drugs to the targeted site of action.

CONCLUSION:

This review provides the information on the numerous strategies used to increase the efficacy and safety of phytomedicines and plant biomarkers. The transdermal formulation will be formulated by using bioactive compounds because of their antimicrobial, antioxidants, antidiabetic, antitumor, anti-inflammatory, anti-psoriatic, Immunobiological activities and wound healing properties. Nanosized drug delivery systems notably enhance the bioavailability and solubility of active ingredients by penetrating vital cellular stocks. The dermal and transdermal drug delivery

systems are aimed to deliver macromolecules and vaccines across the stratum corneum layer using thermal ablation, electroporation, cavitational ultrasound, microdermabrasion, and microneedles. Microfabrication technology has been adapted to produce micron scale needles as a safer and painless alternative to hypodermic needle injections, especially for protein Biotherapeutics and vaccines.

REFERENCES

1. Kalyani Pathak, Dr Ratna Jyoti Das; Dibrugarh university, Assam, India, "An overview on medicinal herbs in the treatment of skin diseases," *World journal of pharmacy and pharmaceutical sciences*; Volume 2, Issue 2, 437-449.
2. Patel Hemangi, Haresh Bhai; department of pharmaceutical quality assurance; Gujarat, India; "Review of herbal plants used in the treatment of skin diseases", *Journal of Pharmacognosy and phytochemistry*; 2021;10(3), 349-356.
3. "Mohammad Nammas; "Systematic review of plant-based excipients in topical drug delivery," Department of applied sciences, Roquette, Lower. Gwynedd township; Pennsylvania; United states; *Ibsonia J med Biomed sci* 2024; 16,162-168.
4. N. Srinivasan; Department of pharmacy, Faculty of engineering and Technology; Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar, Chidambaram, Tamil Nadu, India; "Recent advances in herbal nano formulation: A systematic review. *Asian journal of biological and life sciences*; Volume 12, Issue 1, Jan-Apr, 2023.
5. Jyoti Arsude, Machindra Chavan, Sumit joshi, Shriram Pethakar, Ganesh Dama; Maharashtra, India: "Herbal Nano formulations for topical drug delivery: Prospective for multiple skin disorders,"

- prospective for multiple skin disorders; 04th September 2023, revised:21st October 2023, Accepted: 10th November 2023: 25th December 2023.
6. P. Harika, B.V.P. Deepthi, Vinitha, Ruchi Baherji, Jafar Ali and Dr.J.V.C. Sharma; Joginapally, B.R. Pharmacy College, Yenkapally, Moinabad, Telangana, Hyderabad, India; "Herbal Nanoparticles," volume 7, Issue 3, 2021; "World journal of Pharmaceutical and medical Research".
 7. SitiNuurul Huda Mohammad Azim; Zainuddin Abdul Manan, Sharifah Rafidah wan Alwi, Lee Suan Chua, Azizul Azri Mustaffa and Nor Alafia Yunus; Research Institute of Sustainable Environment (RISE); University Teknologi Malaysia; Johor, Malaysia: "Herbal Processing and Extraction Technologies", Taylor and Francis Group, LLC; 45; 305 – 320, 2016.
 8. SM Kazi, SK Bais, RS Mali, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar technological university; Maharashtra state, India, "Advance herbal Technology," International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Life sciences; 2023, 4(1), 37 – 46.
 9. Gopala Satheesh kumar Kasiramar, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India; Sri Shanmugam college of Pharmacy; "Significant role of Soxhlet Extraction process in Phytochemical Research", Mintage Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Sciences; Volume 7, suppl 1, Jan – Mar 2018.
 10. Pragyana Parimita Mansingh, Lopamudra Adhikari, Moonmun Dhara; Department of Pharma Analysis; School of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Siksha 'O' Anusandhan University, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India; "Herbal Nanoparticles: Commitment towards Contemporary approach," Inc. Pharma.Edu. Res,2023; 57(3S); July to Sep 2023, 465-480.
 11. Mr. Rupesh Bhagwan Khalse, Mr. Ganesh. G. Tapadiya, Saili Prakash Singh Rajput; "Formulation and Evaluation of herbal transdermal patches in treatment of wound healing," International journal of scientific development and Research; September 2022, Volume 7, Issue 9, 675-701.
 12. J. Ashok Kumar, Nikhila Pullakandam, Lakshmana Prabhu, Gopal; "Transdermal drug delivery system: An Overview," International Journal of Scientific development and Research; September 2022, Volume 3, Issue 2, July – August 2010.
 13. Dr. Bijay Kumar Sahoo; "Novel Drug Delivery system," Textbook chapter 1 to 33. www.google.com.
 14. Mehrnaz Abbasi, Braeden Heath; "Iontophoresis and Electroporation assisted microneedles: Advancements and therapeutics potentials in transdermal drug delivery systems," "Drug delivery and Translational Research; 2 October 2024.College of Human Sciences; USA.
 15. Edina Vranic, "Department of Pharmaceutical Technology; Iontophoresis; Fundamentals, Development and Application", Bosnian Journal of Basic Medical Sciences; III (3) 2003.
 16. Jae Hwan Jung, Sung Gyu Jin; "Microneedle for transdermal drug delivery: current trends and Fabrication," Journal of pharmaceutical Investigation (2021) 51; 503 – 517.
 17. Dr. Matthieu Roustit, unite de Pharmacologie Clinique Centre investigation Clinique, Centre, France; "Trails and Tribulations of skin iontophoresis in therapeutics," British Journal of clinical Pharmacology; 21 January 2013; 2 April 2013.
 18. Karmen Cheung, Diganta B. Das; "Microneedles for drug delivery: trends and Progress," Drug delivery Volume 23, 2016, Issue-7.

19. Sarita Singh, Tarique Mahmood Ansari, Vivek Kumar Pandey, and Manju Pandey; Faculty of pharmacy, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India, "The therapeutic potential of herbal infused microneedles formulations and their pivotal rule in disease treatment," *Annals of Phytomedicines*, 13(1), 347 – 352, 2024, An international Journal.
20. "Topical and transdermal drug delivery products," US Pharmacopeia convention, November 1, 2013.
21. B.H. Jaswanth Gowda, Mohammed Gulzar Ahmed, Raghu Raj Singh Thakur, Rayn Donnelly, and Lalit Kumar K. Vora; "Microneedles as an emerging Platform for transdermal delivery of phytochemicals," *Molecular Pharmaceutics*; 2024; 21,6007 to 6033. American chemical society.
22. Mei- Xia Zhao, Bing-Jie Zhu; "The research and applications of quantum dots as nano carriers for targeted drug delivery and cancer therapy", *Zhao and Zhu Nanoscale Research* (2016) 11; 207; 1 to 9.
23. Espacenet.com
24. Google patents
25. www.google.com
26. www.drugs.com
27. Dr.G. Surendra, Dr. Sathvik B, Sridhar, Ramkrishna Reddy, Srikala kami Reddy, Dr. Veeresh; "A Novel drug delivery system through quantum dots in pharmaceutical application-A review; *Journal of chemical Health risks*, JCHR (2024) 14(2), 1485-1493.
28. Naveen Joshi, Sina Azizi, Machekposthi and Roger Narayan; www.jidinnovations.org; "Evolution of transdermal drug delivery devices and novel microneedle Technologies, A historical Perspective and review; 2023, Volume 3, 1 to 10 pages.
29. Wei Kang Luo, Liang Lin Zhang, Zhao Yu Yang, Xiao Hang Guo, Yao Wu, Wei Zhang, Jie Kun Luo, Tao Tang and Yang Wang; *Journal of Nanobiotechnology*; Herbal medicine derived carbon dots: synthesis and applications in therapeutics, bioimaging and sensing, (2021) 19:320; 1 to 30.
30. Neha Bajwa, Neelesh K. Mehra, Keerti Jain & Narendra K. Jain; "Pharmaceutical and biomedical applications of quantum dots," *Artificial Cells, Nanomedicine, and Biotechnology an International Journal*; 2016; 44: 758–768.

HOW TO CITE: K. Swati, Herbal Extracts and Plant Biomarkers: A Promising Approach in Formulation Development of Dermal and Transdermal Dosage Forms, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 7, 1827-1847. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15879012>

